

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CASE REPORT OF WERDNIG-HOFFMANN DISEASE (SPINAL MUSCULAR ATROPHY)

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ABSTRACT

Werdnig-Hoffmann disease (Infantile spinal muscular atrophy) is a genetic disease that manifests itself in early childhood through progressive muscle weakness due to the death of motor neurons in the spinal cord (lower motor neurons). The disease is usually fatal within the first two years of life. The most common cause of death is pneumonia, the development of which is favored by inefficient respiratory movements due to denervation of the diaphragmatic muscles.

We present a case of Werdnig-Hoffman Disease proven by genetic testing, with involvement of higher neuronal groups - basal ganglia, thalamus, brainstem. The disease led to the death of a 6-month-old infant, with the immediate cause - bilateral pneumonia with severe circulatory changes. Morphologically, the microscopic changes typical of the disease in the brain substance at different levels and the damage to the related muscle groups have been confirmed.

Keywords: Werdnig-Hoffman Disease, Spinal Muscular Atrophy, SMA, SMN1 gene mutation.

Introduction

Spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) is a genetic disease that causes degeneration and loss of motor neurons in the brainstem and spinal cord (lower motor neurons), leading to progressive muscle weakness [2]. SMA is the most common fatal recessive disorder in children after cystic fibrosis. SMA is due to a deficiency of a protein encoded by the Survival Motor Neuron (SMN) gene on chromosome 5q11-q13 [5]. The SMN protein is important in the processing of RNA in all cells and has a critical but unknown function in the survival of motor neurons [6]. SMA 1 (infantile or acute SMA; Werdnig-Hoffmann disease) begins in early childhood and is usually fatal within two years [3, 6]. Loss of lower motor neurons causes muscle atrophy from denervation, manifested by severe muscular hypotension, weakness, and inability to breathe [4]. Degenerating brain stem and spinal motor neurons undergo chromatolysis and die [6]. Activated microglial cells often surround and absorb degenerate neurons (neurophage). As the process progresses, replacement gliosis develops. In some cases, SMA 1 affects other neuronal groups - cerebral cortex, basal ganglia, thalamus.

Case report

We present a case of a 6-month-old infant, from first normal pregnancy, born by a normal mechanism. At 2 months age was hospitalized due to reduced physical activity. Generalized muscular hypotension, areflexia of the lower and weakened reflexes of the upper

extremities have been established. Poor control of the head, no ability for turning around. A homozygous deletion of exons 7 and 8 of the SMN1 gene and carrying 2 copies of exons 7 and 8 of the SMN2-reHa was genetically verified. According to the mother, 3-4 days before the hospitalization the child had a high temperature. It is admitted in hospital in unsatisfactory general condition, with groaning nostrils and perioral cyanosis when crying. Respiratory system - paralytic chest, severe kypho-scoliosis, paradoxical respiratory movements, tachydyspnoea up to 80 / min. Neurological status - preserved consciousness, no symptoms of meningo-radicular irritation. Muscle tonus - severe generalized muscle hypotension. There were almost no antigravity movements for the lower limbs, reduced volume of active movements of the upper limbs. There was a lack of foot support and head control. Tendon hypo- to areflexia. Fibrillation of the tongue. During the stay in the intensive care unit the child remains in a serious condition, with signs of respiratory failure, very severe, generalized muscular hypotension and oxygen dependence. Abundant purulent secretions from the oropharynx, requiring frequent aspirations. After a day he showed ineffective breathing, bradycardia, generalized cyanosis and lethal outcome. An autopsy revealed an asymmetry between the left and right parietal bones. An organized cephalohematoma with a dense consistency was found in the right parietal area below the periosteum (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Organized cephalohematoma in the right temporoparietal region

The brain had edematous changes, and the spinal cord was presented with a normal structure, cervical thickening with a diameter of 1 cm, along the length 0.8 cm, with no apparent lumbar thickening. The limbs are

hypotrophic. The thorax was bell-shaped, with deformation and bilateral depression along the axillary lines (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Atrophy of the intercostal muscles and deformities of the ribs

Both lungs were heavy and diffusely compacted. Their surface was purple-red and smooth. At lateral

pressure, a pink foamy liquid appeared from the cut surface (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Bilateral diffuse thickening of the lung, with pronounced hemorrhage and the presence of atelectasis

Materials and methods

The histologic specimens were made with fixative of 10% neutral formaldehyde (formaline) and embedded in paraffin. The cut sections were 4 mkm thick and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (HE).

Results of microscopic examination

Brain and cerebellum - pronounced vascular hyperemia in the meninges, mainly pericellular cerebral edema. Stem nuclei and thalamus - atrophy of neurons, with pycnotic changes in the nuclei (Fig. 4 and 5).

Fig. 4. Stem gray brain nucleus - pycnotic and atrophic neurons, magn. x 200

Fig. 5. Thalamus - pycnotic and atrophic neurons, magn. x 200

Spinal cord: cervical thickening - atrophy, chromatolysis and necrosis in the predominant part of the motor neurons in the anterior horns, areas with replacement gliosis, hypertrophic changes in the single preserved neurons and the presence of micropseudocysts

(Fig. 6); lumbar thickening - atrophy and necrosis of motor neurons in the anterior horns, with replacement gliosis (Fig. 7).

Fig. 6. Spinal cord - cervical thickening - atrophy and necrosis of motor neurons, with gliosis and micropseudocysts, magn. x 200

Fig. 7. - Spinal cord - lumbar thickening - atrophy and necrosis of motor neurons, replacement gliosis, magn. x 200

Skeletal muscles of biceps and quadriceps, intercostal muscles and diaphragm - mosaic changes represented by groups of muscle fibers with severe atrophy,

hypertrophy, replacement fibrosis and areas of lipomatosis (Fig. 8, 9, 10, 11)

Fig. 8. Biceps - groups of muscle fibers with severe atrophy and replacement fibrosis (periphery) and muscle bundles with pronounced hypertrophy (central), magn. x 200.

Fig. 9. Quadriceps femoris - severe atrophy of the muscle bundles, pronounced fibrosis and lipomatosis (central) and hypertrophy of single muscle fibers, magn. x 200

Fig. 10. - Intercostal muscles - severe atrophy with pronounced replacement fibrosis, magn. x 200

Fig. 11. Diaphragm - elongated, stratified, torn and atrophic muscle fibers, magn. x 200

Lungs - extensive atelectatic fields, alternating with single emphysematous areas; severe circulatory changes with fresh and old hemorrhages (Fig. 12); diffuse interstitial inflammatory infiltrates, dominated by

lymphocytes and macrophages and initial interstitial fibrosis (Fig. 13).

Fig. 12. Lungs - atelectasis with severe circulatory changes, magn. x 200

Fig. 13. Lungs - emphysema, interstitial inflammation and initial fibrosis, magn. x 200

Discussion

The autopsy and histological examination confirmed the clinical diagnosis of Spinal muscular atrophy type 1 - Werdnig-Hoffmann disease. The disease has been proven in a lifetime through genetic testing [1, 5]. Morphologically were established severe degenerative changes in the neurons of the basal ganglia, thalamus, brainstem and spinal cord - atrophy, chromatolysis, pycnosis and necrosis, with focal replacement gliosis. Changes in skeletal, intercostal muscles and diaphragm demonstrate a pathognomonic histological model - pronounced diffuse atrophy with replacement fibrosis and compensatory hypertrophy of single muscle bundles [7]. The cause of death was bilateral confluent pneumonia, with atelectasis, hemorrhage, and initial interstitial fibrosis. The development of the inflammatory process in the lung is favored by inefficient respiratory movements due to severe denervation atrophy of the intercostal muscles, as a result of genetically determined destruction of motor neurons at different levels in the brain and spinal cord [1, 6]. The predominance of lymphocytic inflammatory infiltrates in the lungs supports interstitial pneumonia of nonbacterial origin. The cephalohematoma is acquired during childbirth.

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